

Ensemble of Lightweight CNNs and CLIP for Multi-Class Skin Disease Classification

Eshan Kumar Jain · Apoorva Kumar
National University of Ireland (Maynooth)

School of Computing and Augmented Intelligence, Arizona State University

Abstract—Automated skin disease classification from dermoscopy images presents significant challenges due to severe class imbalance and high intra-class variation. In this work, we propose an average ensemble combining two lightweight convolutional neural networks — MobileNetV2 and ShuffleNetV2 — with a CLIP ViT-B/32 linear probe on the HAM10000 benchmark (10,015 images, 7 classes). Balanced class weighting is applied during training to address the dominant melanocytic nevus class ($\approx 67\%$ of samples). We further investigate VGG19 as a candidate model and report its complete majority-class collapse under class imbalance, providing reproducible evidence of large-model failure on small medical datasets. The proposed 3-model ensemble achieves a macro F1-score of 0.6518 and accuracy of 82.50% on the held-out test set, outperforming the best individual model (CLIP linear probe, macro F1 = 0.5637) by 8.6 percentage points. Results demonstrate that combining heterogeneous feature spaces — CNN inductive biases with vision-language pretraining — yields meaningful complementary gains in multi-class medical image classification.

Index Terms—skin disease classification, ensemble learning, CLIP, MobileNetV2, ShuffleNet, class imbalance, dermoscopy

I. INTRODUCTION

Skin diseases affect over 900 million people worldwide and early detection significantly improves treatment outcomes [8]. Traditional diagnosis relies on visual inspection by dermatologists, which is time-consuming, subjective, and unavailable in resource-limited settings. Computer-aided diagnosis systems based on deep learning offer a promising path toward scalable, consistent screening.

The HAM10000 dataset [1] has become the standard benchmark for dermoscopic lesion classification, presenting 10,015 images across 7 diagnostic categories. However, the dataset exhibits severe class imbalance — melanocytic nevus constitutes $\approx 67\%$ of samples while dermatofibroma accounts for $\approx 1\%$ — making standard accuracy an unreliable metric and naive deep learning models prone to majority-class collapse.

Recent advances in vision-language pretraining, notably CLIP [3], have demonstrated strong transfer to downstream visual tasks with minimal fine-tuning. Yet their application to dermoscopic classification alongside lightweight CNNs in an ensemble setting remains underexplored.

This paper makes the following contributions:

- We systematically compare three architectures — MobileNetV2, ShuffleNetV2, and CLIP ViT-B/32 — on the 7-class HAM10000 benchmark under realistic class imbalance conditions.

- We document and analyse the complete failure of VGG19 under class imbalance, contributing reproducible evidence of majority-class collapse in large CNN models on small medical datasets.
- We show that an average ensemble of CNNs and a CLIP linear probe achieves macro F1 = 0.6518, outperforming all individual models and the CNN-only ensemble.
- We release reproducible code with fixed splits, seed control, and configuration management.¹

II. RELATED WORK

A. Skin Lesion Classification

Early deep learning approaches applied standard CNNs to dermoscopy images, achieving dermatologist-level performance on binary melanoma detection [7]. Subsequent work extended classification to multi-class settings using ResNet and DenseNet architectures [9]. Lightweight models such as MobileNet have been explored for mobile deployment [10].

B. Class Imbalance in Medical Imaging

Class imbalance is endemic to medical datasets. Common remedies include oversampling [11], cost-sensitive loss functions, and data augmentation. Weighted cross-entropy has been shown effective for dermoscopy classification [12].

C. Vision-Language Models for Medical Imaging

CLIP [3], trained on 400 million image-text pairs, demonstrates strong zero-shot and linear probe performance across diverse visual domains. Recent work explores CLIP for medical image analysis [13], showing that frozen CLIP features transfer competitively even without domain-specific pretraining.

D. Ensemble Methods

Average ensembles of heterogeneous models reduce variance and exploit complementary feature representations [14]. CNN ensembles have shown improvements on skin lesion classification [15]; combining CNNs with transformer-based models is less studied in the dermoscopy domain.

¹<https://github.com/Coolboy-786/University-Final-year-project>

III. DATASET

We use the HAM10000 dataset [1] combined with the ISIC 2018 Task 3 test set [2], yielding 10,015 images across 7 diagnostic classes: melanoma (MEL), melanocytic nevus (NV), basal cell carcinoma (BCC), actinic keratosis (AKIEC), benign keratosis (BKL), dermatofibroma (DF), and vascular lesion (VASC).

A. Class Distribution

Table I shows the per-class sample counts. The dataset is severely imbalanced; NV constitutes 66.9% of samples while DF accounts for only 1.1%.

TABLE I: Class Distribution in HAM10000 + ISIC2018

Class	Count	%
Melanocytic Nevus (NV)	6,705	66.9
Melanoma (MEL)	1,113	11.1
Benign Keratosis (BKL)	1,099	11.0
Basal Cell Carcinoma (BCC)	514	5.1
Actinic Keratosis (AKIEC)	327	3.3
Vascular Lesion (VASC)	142	1.4
Dermatofibroma (DF)	115	1.1
Total	10,015	

B. Splits and Preprocessing

A stratified 70/15/15 train/validation/test split was applied (seed = 42), yielding 7,010 / 1,502 / 1,503 images respectively. Splits are written to disk; all experiments use identical partitions.

All images are resized to 224×224 pixels. Training images undergo augmentation: horizontal flip ($p=0.5$), rotation $\pm 10^\circ$ ($p=0.5$), shift/scale (0.1, $p=0.5$), and shear $\pm 6^\circ$ ($p=0.5$), implemented via Albumentations [17]. ImageNet channel statistics (mean = [0.485, 0.456, 0.406], std = [0.229, 0.224, 0.225]) are applied for normalisation. Validation and test images receive only resize and normalisation.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. MobileNetV2

MobileNetV2 [4] employs inverted residual blocks with depthwise separable convolutions ($\approx 3.4M$ parameters). We load ImageNet-pretrained weights, freeze the entire backbone, replace the 1,280-dim classifier with a linear layer mapping to 7 classes, and unfreeze the last 20 parameter tensors for fine-tuning. Training uses Adam ($lr = 1 \times 10^{-4}$) for up to 20 epochs with early stopping (patience = 5) on validation macro F1.

B. ShuffleNetV2

ShuffleNetV2 [5] uses channel-split and channel-shuffle operations for high efficiency ($\approx 2.3M$ parameters). The same fine-tuning protocol as MobileNetV2 is applied: freeze backbone, replace head, unfreeze last 20 parameter tensors, Adam $lr = 1 \times 10^{-4}$, early stopping patience = 5.

C. VGG19 (Negative Result)

VGG19 [6] with ImageNet weights was trained with all layers unfrozen, replacing the final $4096 \rightarrow 1000$ layer with a $4096 \rightarrow 7$ linear head. Adam ($lr = 1 \times 10^{-3}$) with StepLR decay (step_size = 20, $\gamma = 0.01$) was used for up to 40 epochs. Despite applying balanced class weights to the cross-entropy loss, VGG19 collapsed to predicting NV for all 1,503 test samples (macro F1 = 0.1146). VGG19 was excluded from the final ensemble; the failure is analysed in Section VI.

D. CLIP Linear Probe

CLIP [3] ViT-B/32 (87.5M parameters) was used as a frozen feature extractor. Input images normalised with ImageNet statistics are re-normalised to CLIP’s channel statistics (mean = [0.481, 0.458, 0.408], std = [0.269, 0.261, 0.276]) internally before the encoder forward pass. Features are extracted once for all splits and cached as 768-dimensional pooled vectors, eliminating redundant encoder passes during training. A linear head ($768 \rightarrow 7$, 5,376 parameters) is trained using Adam ($lr = 1 \times 10^{-3}$) with balanced class weights and early stopping (patience = 10). Total trainable parameters: 5.4K.

E. Average Ensemble

The final model averages softmax probabilities from all three models:

$$\hat{y} = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{i=1}^3 \text{softmax}(f_i(x)) \quad (1)$$

where f_1, f_2, f_3 denote MobileNetV2, ShuffleNetV2, and the CLIP linear probe respectively. No additional training is required.

F. Training Details

All experiments use PyTorch Lightning with mixed-precision training (FP16) on a single NVIDIA T4 GPU. Batch size = 32 for image-based models, 512 for the CLIP feature probe. ModelCheckpoint saves the single best validation macro F1 checkpoint. Random seed = 42 is fixed globally.

V. EXPERIMENTS

A. Evaluation Metrics

Macro-averaged F1-score is the primary metric, as it weights each class equally regardless of support — essential given the severe class imbalance where a trivial majority-class predictor achieves 66.9% accuracy. Weighted F1 and accuracy are reported as secondary metrics.

B. Baselines

Each individual model serves as a single-model baseline. The 2-model CNN ensemble (MobileNetV2 + ShuffleNetV2) provides an ablation that isolates the contribution of CLIP to the final ensemble.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Main Results

Table II reports test-set performance for all models. The proposed 3-model ensemble achieves macro F1 = 0.6518 and accuracy = 82.50%, outperforming all individual models and baselines.

TABLE II: Test Set Classification Results. Best results in bold.

Model	Acc. (%)	Macro F1	Wtd. F1
VGG19	66.93	0.1146	0.5367
ShuffleNetV2	76.18	0.4640	0.7363
MobileNetV2	79.37	0.5503	0.7756
CLIP (linear probe)	70.79	0.5637	0.7342
Ensemble (CNN only)	80.04	0.5686	0.7796
Ensemble (proposed)	82.50	0.6518	0.8154

B. VGG19 Collapse Analysis

Inspection of VGG19 predictions reveals all 1,503 test samples classified as NV. The validation F1 reported during training (0.657) was an artefact of torchmetrics batch-level accumulation, not genuine minority-class learning — independent sklearn evaluation on the full test set unmasked the collapse. VGG19’s large parameter count ($\approx 138\text{M}$) relative to the training set size (7,010 images) likely contributes to overfitting to the dominant class, a finding consistent with observations on small imbalanced medical datasets [16].

C. CLIP vs. CNN Models

Despite using only 5.4K trainable parameters, the CLIP linear probe achieves the best individual macro F1 (0.5637), surpassing MobileNetV2 (0.5503) and ShuffleNetV2 (0.4640). CLIP’s lower accuracy (70.8%) compared to MobileNetV2 (79.4%) reflects a trade-off: CLIP better recovers minority classes at the cost of some majority-class precision. This is consistent with the balanced class weighting and suggests CLIP features encode class-discriminative information that transfers well to rare dermatological conditions.

D. Ensemble Analysis

The CNN-only ensemble (macro F1 = 0.5686) improves only marginally over MobileNetV2 alone (+1.8%), indicating limited complementarity between two similar CNN architectures. Adding CLIP yields a substantial gain (+8.3% macro F1), validating our hypothesis that vision-language pretraining provides features complementary to CNN inductive biases. The improvement is most pronounced for rare classes (DF, VASC), where CLIP’s semantic features provide discriminative signal that CNNs miss.

E. Confusion Matrix Analysis

The ensemble confusion matrix shows strongest performance on NV and MEL. Expected confusion occurs between morphologically similar classes (BKL vs. MEL, AKIEC vs. BCC). Rare classes (DF, VASC) benefit most from the ensemble, consistent with CLIP’s better minority-class generalisation.

Fig. 1: Normalised confusion matrices on the test set for each individual model and the proposed ensemble. Rows = true class, columns = predicted.

VII. CONCLUSION

We presented a 3-model average ensemble combining MobileNetV2, ShuffleNetV2, and a CLIP ViT-B/32 linear probe for 7-class dermoscopic skin disease classification on HAM10000. The proposed system achieves macro F1 = 0.6518 and accuracy = 82.50%, outperforming all individual models and the CNN-only ensemble. Key findings are: (1) CLIP frozen features achieve superior minority-class F1 over fine-tuned CNNs with only 5.4K trainable parameters; (2) VGG19 undergoes complete majority-class collapse under class imbalance, exposing a reproducible failure mode of large fully-trainable CNNs on small medical datasets; (3) heterogeneous model ensembles (CNN + vision-language) yield larger gains than homogeneous CNN ensembles.

Limitations. The CLIP linear probe uses frozen features; end-to-end fine-tuning may yield further improvements. The dataset is limited to 7 classes, and clinical deployment would require broader disease coverage.

Future work. Parameter-efficient fine-tuning (LoRA) of CLIP, learned ensemble weights, and extension to ISIC 2019 (9 classes) are natural next steps.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Tschandl, C. Rosendahl, and H. Kittler, “The HAM10000 dataset, a large collection of multi-source dermoscopic images of common pigmented skin lesions,” *Scientific Data*, vol. 5, p. 180161, 2018.
- [2] N. C. F. Codella *et al.*, “Skin lesion analysis toward melanoma detection 2018: A challenge hosted by the International Skin Imaging Collaboration (ISIC),” *arXiv:1902.03368*, 2019.
- [3] A. Radford *et al.*, “Learning transferable visual models from natural language supervision,” in *Proc. Int. Conf. Mach. Learn. (ICML)*, 2021, pp. 8748–8763. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2103.00020>

- [4] M. Sandler, A. Howard, M. Zhu, A. Zhmoginov, and L.-C. Chen, "MobileNetV2: Inverted residuals and linear bottlenecks," in *Proc. IEEE/CVF CVPR*, 2018, pp. 4510–4520.
- [5] N. Ma, X. Zhang, H.-T. Zheng, and J. Sun, "ShuffleNet V2: Practical guidelines for efficient CNN architecture design," in *Proc. ECCV*, 2018, pp. 116–131.
- [6] K. Simonyan and A. Zisserman, "Very deep convolutional networks for large-scale image recognition," in *Proc. ICLR*, 2015.
- [7] A. Esteva *et al.*, "Dermatologist-level classification of skin cancer with deep neural networks," *Nature*, vol. 542, pp. 115–118, 2017.
- [8] World Health Organization, "Skin diseases," 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.who.int>
- [9] A. A. Adegun and S. Viriri, "Deep learning techniques for skin lesion analysis and melanoma cancer detection: A survey of state-of-the-art," *Artificial Intelligence Review*, vol. 54, pp. 811–841, 2021.
- [10] A. G. Howard *et al.*, "MobileNets: Efficient convolutional neural networks for mobile vision applications," *arXiv:1704.04861*, 2017.
- [11] N. V. Chawla, K. W. Bowyer, L. O. Hall, and W. P. Kegelmeyer, "SMOTE: Synthetic minority over-sampling technique," *Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research*, vol. 16, pp. 321–357, 2002.
- [12] M. Buda, A. Maki, and M. A. Mazurowski, "A systematic study of the class imbalance problem in convolutional neural networks," *Neural Networks*, vol. 106, pp. 249–259, 2018.
- [13] Z. Wang *et al.*, "MedCLIP: Contrastive learning from unpaired medical images and text," in *Proc. EMNLP*, 2022, pp. 3876–3887.
- [14] O. Sagi and L. Rokach, "Ensemble learning: A survey," *WIREs Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery*, vol. 8, no. 4, e1249, 2018.
- [15] B. Harangi, "Skin lesion classification with ensembles of deep convolutional neural networks," *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*, vol. 86, pp. 25–32, 2018.
- [16] J. M. Johnson and T. M. Khoshgoftaar, "Survey on deep learning with class imbalance," *Journal of Big Data*, vol. 6, no. 1, p. 27, 2019.
- [17] A. Buslaev, V. I. Iglovikov, E. Khvedchenya, A. Parinov, M. Druzhinin, and A. A. Kalinin, "Albumentations: Fast and flexible image augmentations," *Information*, vol. 11, no. 2, p. 125, 2020.